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Training course in human anatomy: Experience report

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Abstract

This work discusses the experience obtained in the extension project entitled "Training Course in Human Anatomy", provided by the Human Anatomy League (LAMAH) of the Federal University of Piauí (UFPI). The objective of this work is to expose the experience of nursing students facing the training course, highlighting the advantages and obstacles encountered. An active methodology was chosen, in which students shared their knowledge about each system with other members during meetings, in an active teaching-learning system. Thus, we infer that the methodology both provides a new experience and contributes positively to a better absorption and retention of the contents seen. However, an obstacle observed in the meetings was evidenced by the gap in the handling and mastery of natural anatomical pieces. Furthermore, the extension activity presented here constitutes an object to support the authors' knowledge of Human Anatomy.

Keywords: Academic qualification; Human anatomy; Active methodology; Post-pandemic

1. Introduction

Academic Leagues are student entities that, associated with the monitoring of professors or professionals linked to an institution, have non-profit functions of unlimited duration, which aim to improve the knowledge and techniques acquired at graduation in a specific learning area, with the aim of integrating students from different courses and periods that demonstrate interest in this field [1].

These leagues are based on the university tripod, which is based on the association between teaching, research and extension. In this way, these organizations value the transmission of theoretical and practical content in an orderly manner, positively adding to their academic training and helping to constantly encourage the search for new information by their participants for the construction of solid knowledge. In addition, there is also an interconnection between university activities and society through projects carried out and organized by the league that contribute to the spread of academic knowledge and fulfill its social commitment [2].

The discipline of Human Anatomy is a classic and indispensable content for courses in the health area such as medicine, nursing, dentistry, physical education, pharmacy, nutrition, psychology and others, since for these professionals it is necessary and extremely important the good understanding of the parts that make up the human body, because, in order to care for, rehabilitate or diagnose it is necessary to have knowledge about the human standard [3].

The new Coronavirus pandemic had an influence on several social spheres, including higher education, as the activities offered within universities had to be readapted for distance learning through online platforms [4]. Therefore, as a way of adapting to the post pandemic moment and as a way to contribute to the knowledge of students who did not have the

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possibility of direct contact with the laboratory of morphology in UFPI, the Multiprofessional Academic League of Human Anatomy of the Federal University of Piauí (LAMAHA-UFPI) promoted the creation of the Training Course in Human Anatomy, in the face-to-face modality, since many students did not have the opportunity to witness such experiences.

In this way, the presentation of the structures of the human body in natural and artificial anatomical parts was provided at the Department of Morphology at UFPI, an approximation of theory with practice, which gives students a more in-depth knowledge about this content. Thus, the present study aims to report the experience of nursing students, facing the Training Course in Human Anatomy offered by LAMAHA in order to contribute positively to the teaching and learning process through the knowledge acquired from this experience.

2. Material and methods

This is a descriptive experience report about the extension course entitled "Training Course in Human Anatomy" provided by the Multiprofessional Academic League of Human Anatomy of the Federal University of Piauí (LAMAHA-UFPI), in Teresina-Piauí, Brazil. This course was carried out under the guidance of the league directors and the report is based on the method of shared knowledge construction, which consists of collectively forming knowledge with the objective of transforming health actions both in theoretical and practical scope [5].

From this perspective, the course participants were divided into three groups, with practical classes, on Mondays and Fridays, in the human anatomy laboratory of the morphology department, according to the availability of ligands. In each class, totaling three for each group, the members were divided into pairs and trios, each one being responsible for presenting to the other members, one of the human body systems, such as the respiratory, digestive and cardiac, through natural and artificial anatomical pieces available in the laboratory, including: heart, lungs, kidneys, liver and various muscles. The classes put into practice the theoretical knowledge of the members, proposing an active teaching methodology.

In the fourth meeting, a practical test was carried out, in the form of a gymkhana, in which each participant had to identify the names of parts of anatomical pieces of different systems of the human body. Each student should stand on a bench for one minute and identify the structure marked by white and blue pins, writing down their answer on a blank sheet of paper. At the end of the set time, the students changed benches and, so on, until the end of the activity. In this way, the test aimed to evaluate the knowledge acquired during classes and provide students with the first contact with this assessment, already traditionally applied in the Human Anatomy discipline at UFPI and which was carried out remotely during the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. Results and discussion

Human Anatomy is a science of extreme importance for all health professionals, and it has undergone several changes in the way of teaching in educational institutions, considering that even though it is still used, the implementation of studies through cadavers has been decreasing, and increasing, respectively, the construction of anatomical replicas, records in images and books showing in detail each of the anatomical structures of the human body [6].

Thus, the related report shows that the way of approaching the practical classes of the extension course, has a substantial relevance, as it provides the binders with a motivation to be managers of their own teaching-learning process, since they are stimulated to break with traditional teaching methods. In addition, it can provide greater contact with laboratories of anatomy to students who did not have this experience, due to the pandemic period, when remote teaching was applied.

Thus, it is clear that the methodology applied in the practical classes of the league was advantageous for its members, given that the practice in the laboratories of anatomy is an effective way of keeping in touch with reality, providing a broader and more effective learning process. Just as the elaboration of support materials acts in an alternative and complementary way, the presentation of seminars contributes to creating didactic ways of teaching, and the realization of the practical test in the form of a gymkhana allows the binders to be stimulated to train themselves more and more, always looking for creative or unconventional ways to learn and fix each content.

Therefore, the effectiveness of teaching-learning was observed through the use of these different methodological strategies, as it was able to provide the development of different forms of communication, using visual resources, texts,

drawings, associations between books and manipulation of anatomical parts, increasing the ability to capture anatomical details, textures, correlations between organs [6].

However, it was found that, even if the use of different methodologies has favored a better absorption of the content, the use of natural pieces could still have been more present, helping even more in the fixation of each system of the human body. However, this fact did not significantly affect the experience provided by the extension course, since the other activities were effectively complementary.

4. Conclusion

The active methodology adopted contributed to a better absorption and retention of content, in addition, it also favored a new perspective on the learning-teaching experience provided during the meetings. Furthermore, the extension activity presented in this study constituted an extremely important support object for the absorption of knowledge about Human Anatomy from its students.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest, as this work is purely for the purpose of promoting the strengthening of teaching and learning.

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